

INTEGRATED USE OF GEOELECTRICAL IMAGING AND GEOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS IN THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF EGBE DUMPSITE IN IJEBU-IGBO AREA/ SOUTH WESTERN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The impact of solid waste disposal at Egbe area of Ijebu-igbo, southwestern Nigeria on the adjoining surface and groundwater sources has been investigated. The Basement rocks in the area include Precambrian Migmatite gneiss complex, Older granite that have been extensively weathered. In the study area, the geophysical survey involved three (3) electrical imaging line while the hydro chemical database comprised two samples of hand-dug wells and one sample of surface water. The result of the interpretation of the electrical imaging lines shows the thickness of the dumpsite to be shallow at about 5m with low apparent resistivity varying from 10-30 ohm-m, 65-85 ohm-m in the northwestern and southeastern part; of traverse 1 and 10-30 ohm-m on the north western part of traverse 2. The apparent resistivity increase with depth and this shows that the leachates of the dumpsite indicated by low apparent resistivity is not likely to affect the aquifer system because of the presence of the lateritic cap in the subsurface. The third traverse, which serves as the control, has high apparent resistivity and this indicates absence of leachates but weathered basement. Result of chemical analysis carried out on the water samples show that the surface and groundwater at the vicinity of the dumpsite has not been polluted and this is likely due to the shallow depth or thickness of the dumpsite. In conclusion, the proposed housing estate in the study area can still go on without fear of water pollution by the presence of the abandoned dumpsite.

KEY WORD: Integrated, Geoelectrics, Geochemistry, Environment, Impa assessment, Dumpsite.

INTRODUCTION

General statement

The environment at which waste is disposed poses a major problem on ground water. The environment of disposal is referring to as dumpsite and is defined as a place where accumulations of refuse or other discarded materials are dumped. A survey by World Health organization (WHO, 1996) revealed that in developing countries in 1970, only 40% of the people in rural area had access to safe water. Solid wastes disposed of in a dumpsite are of two types; hazardous and non- hazardous wastes. Hazardous waste is composed of toxic explosive generally industrial wastes while household wastes such as glass, plastic and social wastes constitute the non hazardous wastes. This household wastes is also refer to as municipal wastes. The Egbe area in Ijebu-Igbo, the study area the dumpsite is a non-hazardous waste dumpsite and it is an open dump system. At present the dumpsite has been abandoned after 17years of operation.

Disposal of refuse occurs all over the world and proves to be a major problem. Careless dumping of refuse and poor management can greatly affect one's health. Poor management of disposal site forms breeding place of mosquitoes, houseflies, pathogenic micro organism and rats and these lead to diseases such as cholera, malaria and diarrhea (Abua, 1996). Pollution from solid wastes always begins with precipitates carrying the leachates into land surface and ends with the water reaching surface water or ground water. Precipitate on the refuse dumpsite will either infiltrate the refuse or run off over as land flow. During the vertical percolation process (with rain water) the water leaches both organic and inorganic constituents from refuse. The leachates become part of the ground water flow system immediately they reach the water

TABLE 1. Physical and chemical parameters of water samples on the study area.

PARAMETERS	WELL 1	WELL 2.	WELL 3.	STREAM
pH	6.78	5.81	6.11	5.87
Total Dissolved Solids	96	72	85	34
Electrical Conductivity	166	110	132	55
Total Acidity	8	12	12	12
Total Hardness	60	50	60	20
Calcium	22.4	14.4	17.0	5.6
Magnesium	0.77	3.4	3.89	1.46
Sodium	3.56	2.67	2.08	1.26
Total Iron	0.11	0.13	0.17	0.26
Sulphate	1.80	1.65	1.76	1.81
Nitrate	2.58	3.37	2.74	2.09
Chloride	6.00	5.25	6.12	5.74
Silica	2.03	3.90	2.14	2.35
Bicarbonate	32	24	28	24

Location, Accessibility and Physiography.

The study area, Egbe in Ijebu-Igbo is situated in southwestern Nigeria and lies in latitudes 6° 55' and 6°70'N and Longitudes 3° 50' and 3° 57'East. The area is accessible with untarred road leading to the dumpsite from the main road in the area (Fig. 1)

The study area is characterized by a tropical climate with alternating wet and dry seasons. The area has double maximum of rainfall and the peak being June and September while the dry season last from November to early March (Akanni, 1992) the temperature ranges between 32°C - 21°C throughout the year. Due to the climate conditions of the area, the vegetation is typical rainforest vegetation. The relief of the study environment is moderately high and it has a gradient of approximately 1/600 giving a nearly flat topography. Shanu (1991), Adeyemi (1995) noted that landform such as relief, surface morphology and drainage systems depends to a large extent on the difference in the composition of rocks and the frequency of joints and fissures in rocks.

The drainage pattern of the area is that of which is structurally control type.

Geology and Hydrogeology of the area.

Geologically, Ijebu-Igbo is part of the South Western Nigeria basement complex (Fig. 2). The area studied is a representative of both the migmatite gneiss complex and the older granite, which shows structural disposition (Rahaman, 1976). The Migmatite gneiss complex occupies the southwestern part and the southeastern parts of the area while older granite occupies the Norm, East and some part of western area. The basement complex is poor aquifers when in unaltered form because of their low porosity and permeability. The occurrence of groundwater in this environment is largely due to occurrence of secondary porosity and permeability resulting from weathering and fracturing of the rocks. The nature and thickness of the overburden also play important role on the availability of groundwater. If the overburden occur as loose aggregate as sands, it allows percolation of water into it so the extent of such overlying materials, thus indicate the amount of groundwater in the subsurface (Olurunfemi, et. al, (1999).

MATERIALS AND METHOD OF INVESTIGATION

Two methods were adopted during the research with. There are geophysical and geochemical methods. The geophysical method involves the use of electrical resistivity method. A total of 3 constant separation traverses (CST) were established using Wenner array and with a minimum spacing of 5 m (Fig. 3)

TABLE 2. Comparison of water sample of the study area with “who” standard

PARAMETERS	RANGE	MEAN	WHO STANDARD
pH	5.81- 6.78	6.14	6.5-9.2
Total Dissolved Solids	34-96	72	1000-1500
Electrical Conductivity	55 - 166	116	NA
Total Acidity	8-12	11	NA
Total Hardness	20-60	48	100-300
Calcium	5.6-22.4	14.9	75-200
Magnesium	0.77-3.89	2.38	50-150
Sodium	1.26-3.56	2.39	150-200
Total Iron	0.11-0.26	0.17	0.3-1.0
Sulphate	1.65-1.81	1.76	250-400
Nitrate	2.09-3.37	2.70	50-100
Chloride	5.25-6.12	5.78 •	250 - 600
Silica	2.03-3.90	2.61	20-?
Bicarbonate	24-32	27	600 -?

NA= Not available

Two traverses (T1, T2) were taking directly on the waste dumpsite, the third traverses; T3 was occupied outside the dumpsite in order to serve as a control for the first two traverses. In order to supplement apparent resistivity data, especially in providing near- surface information, a vertical electrical sounding (VES) was conducted. The distance between the first two traverses in 28m and the third is 30m away from the second traverses and dumpsite. The results obtained were used in contouring Wenner pseudosection for the surface area.

While geochemical method involve the collection of water samples from the available well in the study area. Major cations and anions were analyzed to determine the level of their contamination. The result obtained was compared with the International standard for drinking water after "WHO" in order to determined the level of contamination (If any) and the quality of the water.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The resistivity data are presented as contoured pseudo section while the VES data was used to determine the depth to bedrock in the area. The results of geochemical are shown in table 1.

As shown in the contoured pseudo section for traverses 1 (Fig. 4a), low apparent resistivity values were observed between 10-30 ohm- m on the Northwest part and 65 - 85 ohm - m on the Southeastern part of the traverses. The low apparent resistivity is assumed to be derived from high conductivity of leachate that occurs at shallow depth as shown in the pseudo section. The apparent resistivity then increase with depth, this is a reflection of the weathered bedrock.

Traverse 2, T2 that is about 28m from traverse 1 but on the dumpsite also shows low apparent resistivity value between 10-30 ohm- m on the Northwest part of the traverse line (Fig 4b). This also suggests presence of leachate materials at shallow depth. The apparent resistivity values then tend to increase with depth, which is similar to T1.

The control traverses line, T3 about 60m away from T1 show high apparent resistivity at shallow depth indicating absence of leachate materials (Fig 4c).

From the VES data, four geoelectric compares were identified - the topsoil having resistivity of 92 ohm-m and thickness of 0.7m; this value is a reflection of presence of leachate materials at shallow depth. The second and the third layers are made of lateritic/ sandy materials while the fourth layer of resistivity 455ohm-m in the basement rock. The overburden thickness obtained is 19.53m. The presence of leachate at shallow depth as seen in the study area is not likely to affect the aquifer system because of the presence of the lateritic cap in the area. From the result of chemical analysis, it was observe that major element such as Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , Fe^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , Cl^- , and HCO_3^- , have low concentration and fall below the minimum permissible level of the "WHO" standard (Table 2).

The low value of total dissolved solids (TDS), Nitrate and Chloride shows that there is no contamination of the water resources by the presence of lactates from the dumpsite (Ariyo, 2005). Therefore there is no impact of lactates on the water quality, hence, the water resources in the study area is still portable.

CONCLUSION

The integrated uses of geoelectrical imaging and hydrochemistry have made it possible to establish the probable limit of leachate zone.

On the basis of chemical analysis, it is observed that the water resources has not being polluted by the refuse dumpsite due to the shallow thickness of the dumpsite as revealed from geoelectric pseudosection and vertical electrical sounding results. It can therefore be rightly concluded that, the dumpsite at Egbe is presently not a source of pollution to the water (surface and ground water) resources in the area and can be therefore be used as the housing estate as proposed by the State government. Periodic investigation involving geoelectrical and geochemical methods should be carrying out at intervals of time to monitor possible pollution from the waste dumpsite of the study area.

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